

Pest resistance—other pests

Resistance of deepwater rice (DWR) varieties to ufra disease in Assam

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We field-tested 100 DWR varieties and breeding lines to determine their resistance to ufra disease, caused by *Ditylenchus angustus*, during 1989 and

1990 wet seasons (Apr/May–Oct/Nov).

We sowed seeds in 10-m rows at 20 × 20-cm spacing in an ufra-infected area. Susceptible checks Rangabao and NC492 were planted in rows alternately with test entries. Local agronomic practices were followed. Susceptibility was expressed as the percentage of infected tillers/hill (see table).

Rangabao and NC492 averaged 90% infected tillers/hill, which led to total crop collapse. □

Reaction of DWR varieties to ufra disease in Assam, India, 1989-90 wet seasons.

Entries	Ufra incidence (% infected tillers/hill)	Reaction class
Rayada 16-06	0	Resistant
Rayada 16-05	11–25	Moderately resistant
Rayada 16-07		
Rayada 16-08		
Rayada 16-09		
Bazail 65		
Neghri, Laldhepa, Panikekua, Herepi, Duatkalam, Maguri	26–50	Susceptible
Padmapani (red), Padmapani (white)		Escaped disease because of early crop maturity (Sep)
Adalibao, Amona, ARC/152, ARC5778, Badam, Badel, Bagadhhepa, Bakul, Bordhan, Buralibao, Bogphul, Beta, Borjahingia, Bogajul, Biroi, Bormaguri, Chengabao, CR670-37, CR671-19, Dalbao, Dolmaguri, Digabao, Dhepabao, Dubaribao, Dubraj, FRG7, Gajepsali, Hatisali, Harkana, Hida, HBA 1, Indunayan, Ikarasali, IET10003, IET10005, IET10006, IET10008, IET10021, IET10027, IET11181, IET10048, IR48193-20-3, IR42580-13-2, IR47393-306, IR47619-20-3, IR11141-6-1-4, Julbao, Katibao, Kajalibao, Kekua, Kehjol, Kalamani, Laodubi, Khamtisali, Latamaguri, LPR85, LPR372, LPR56-97-115, LPR56-203-18, LPR56-304-38, LPR96-10, LPR254-164, LPR302-94-68, LPR425-42-116, LPR550-387-24, Mahsuri, Monoharsali, Moimonsingia, Neghri, NC492, ND4R21, Panimaguri, Patki, PJNB96-10, PJNB95-2, PJNB94-18-1, PN56-205-43-12, Rangabao, Rengunsali, Rupahi, Sonamukhi, Solpona, Sorsori, Tarabao, Tulasibao	50	Highly susceptible

Stress tolerance

Low light tolerance of rice hybrids and their pollen parents

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The productivity of F₁ rice hybrids under low-light conditions during monsoon season has not been well analyzed.

We studied tolerance for low light in eight hybrids derived from CMS sources V20 A, IR54752 A, and Intan Mutant A (IMA), their pollen parents (restored) and checks (Ratna and Swarnaprabha) during 1990 wet season. Plants were spaced at 15 × 10 cm in 1.2 m² field plots and fertilized with 60 kg N/ha.

Plants were shaded with wood screens from 40 d after planting to harvest to simulate low light (50% normal) conditions. Controls were maintained under normal sunlight (about 320 cal/cm² per d). The experiment was replicated three times and laid out in a split-plot design. Light treatments were in main plots, and hybrids and pollen parents in subplots. Growth duration of hybrids varied from 117 to 145 d (see table).

Photosynthetic rate (Pn) was measured with the Li-6000 Portable Photosynthesis system under optimal light of about 900 μE/m² per s. Crop photosynthesis was the product of Pn and leaf area index (LAI). Both Pn and Pn × LAI were generally higher in IR54752 A hybrids, especially in IR54752 A/Vajram. It also had the highest dry matter, yield, and harvest index under both normal light and low light. Such efficiency may be attributed to higher physiological and yield potential of the restorer. Yield per day of hybrids and parent were also highest in both light regimes.

IR54752 A/Vajram showed significant standard heterosis in yield under low light compared with the best low light-tolerant check Swarnaprabha. Yield heterosis over its restorer, though negligible under normal light, was considerable under low light (10%).